

Business applications of Artificial Intelligence

Creative industries
briefing paper

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

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About the briefing paper series

A significant barrier to AI adoption in the business world is the scarcity of clear, accessible information on how to leverage AI to enhance organisational productivity. Understanding the practical applications of AI is a prerequisite for companies to identify relevant opportunities and develop a strategy to operationalise them. To address this need, the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team at The Alan Turing Institute is pursuing a research project to illuminate how businesses in the four BridgeAI priority sectors of agriculture, forestry and fishing, construction, creative industries, and transportation and storage can leverage AI to be more productive.

The first milestone of this project is the publication of a framework for categorising and analysing business applications of AI and a brief analysis of sector-specific AI use cases. Our findings are published as a **series of five documents**: four sector-specific briefings complemented by a paper presenting a framework to categorise and analyse AI use cases. The sector briefings offer a short analysis of the high-level economic features of each

sector in the UK, the specific challenges to AI adoption faced by businesses in that sector, and five business applications of AI per sector. Each sector brief can be read as a standalone document. The paper on the classification framework presents the tool that we developed to categorise and analyse AI use cases in a business context. In addition to providing the hermeneutical structure underpinning our research, this tool provides a valuable resource for businesses trying to identify relevant AI opportunities. Companies can use this framework as a starting point to build on and develop their bespoke methodology to identify, select, and implement the right AI solutions.

The second milestone of this project will be to refine the framework based on feedback collected after the publication of this first exploratory version and expand its scope to include information about the risks connected to each AI use case and the mitigation strategies that can be adopted to address those risks in that specific context.

Desired impact

Our research aims to support businesses at the early stages of their AI adoption cycle. By providing a conceptual framework to systematically categorise business applications of AI and offering concrete examples of sector-specific AI applications, we hope to help businesses identify possible uses of AI in their area, understand the nature of relevant technological solutions, and develop a sound strategy to operationalise those solutions responsibly.

Intended audience

The audience for this briefing series is primarily businesses within the BridgeAI priority sectors looking to adopt AI to support their operations. It is worth noting that the accompanying framework was developed based on generalised principles which are applicable to any sector and should, therefore, provide value to a wider audience, including non-commercial organisations. In addition to benefiting companies, this briefing series provides valuable resources for government officials and regulators aiming to understand how businesses use AI, as well as for training officers and advisors seeking a systematic approach to developing AI strategies for business.

AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team

This work has been completed by researchers from The Alan Turing Institute who are part of the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team based within the Public Policy programme. As part of our offering for the BridgeAI programme, we support UK businesses navigate the increasingly complex AI governance landscape. This is delivered through training and sector-specific research on some of the most pressing AI governance issues, as well as by engaging with regional AI policy stakeholders to help consolidate a nationwide community of actors invested in responsible AI governance.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the global economy, yet many sectors of the business world are only beginning to explore the opportunities AI technologies offer. Despite AI adoption being on the rise globally, the technology's potential to support organisations by improving their productivity and competitiveness remains partially unexplored in many economic areas. For instance, only 20% of small companies in the UK say they use at least one AI tool as part of their operations, despite 55% stating that AI could provide benefits to their business.¹ To ensure AI will benefit a wide range of sectors and regions and support businesses in their AI adoption journey, the UK government launched several high-impact initiatives to “invest and plan for the long-term needs of the [country's] AI ecosystem”.² These include, among others, the BridgeAI programme, which aims to foster the development and adoption of AI technologies in sectors with high potential for AI-driven economic transformation.³

Despite important steps forward, several barriers to widespread AI adoption still exist. These include the high cost of AI solutions, the uncertainty of their return on investment,⁴ the scarcity of relevant technical and business skills in the labour market,⁵ regulatory uncertainty

related to the development and use of AI,⁶ low rates of senior management buy-in, the difficulty of collecting or accessing high-quality data,⁷ and scepticism for some AI applications caused by ethical concerns around issues such as bias and privacy. At a more fundamental level, many companies struggle to identify the right AI opportunities due to a general lack of awareness about the full range of practical business applications of these technologies. In other words, many companies are unsure about how exactly to leverage the potential of AI to support their business goals. For instance, a recent survey of 100 business leaders from different countries and sectors found that while “leaders are overwhelmingly looking at AI as an opportunity, the picture is not yet clear on how to harness this opportunity practically.”⁸

One way to address this uncertainty is disseminating knowledge about existing AI use cases and best practices in the industry. Understanding how other companies use AI technologies, be it to support internal functions or to build better products and services, enables businesses that are considering embarking on the journey of AI adoption to think creatively about how AI can add value to their organisation.

1 Russell, C. & E. Quist (2024). *Redefining intelligence: The growth of AI among small businesses*. Federation of Small Businesses. <https://www.fsb.org.uk/resource-report/redefining-intelligence.html>.

2 UK Government (2021). *National AI Strategy*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>.

3 Innovate UK (2023). *BridgeAI*. <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/bridgeai/>.

4 CDEI (2021). *UK Business Innovation Survey*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/61bb2e77e90e07044462d8b7/Business_Innovation_Survey_2021.pdf.

5 *AI ecosystem survey informing the National AI Strategy*. The Alan Turing Institute, https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/ai-strategy-survey_results_020921.pdf.

6 Gillespie, N., S. Lockey, C. Curtis, et al. (2023). *Trust in Artificial Intelligence: A global study*. The University of Queensland and KPMG Australia. https://policy-futures.centre.uq.edu.au/files/16650/Trust%20in%20AI%20Global%20Report_2023_UQ.pdf.

7 Mittal, N., Saif, I. & Ammanath, B. (2022). *Fueling the AI transformation: Four key actions powering widespread value from AI, right now*. Deloitte, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/deloitte-analytics/us-ai-institute-state-of-ai-fifth-edition.pdf>.

8 Bicakci, B. et al. (2024). *Leadership in the Age of AI*. EgonZehnder and Kearney. <https://www.egonzehnder.com/leadership-in-the-age-of-ai>.

Building on this premise, this briefing aims to contribute to demystifying how businesses in the creative industries can use AI to be more competitive, sustainable, and productive. The first part of the briefing offers an overview of the key economic features of the UK's creative industries, including a brief discussion of sector-specific challenges to AI adoption. In the second part, we leverage the **AI use case classification framework** to discuss five sectoral AI applications. Each AI use case is accompanied by a use case card, which provides a visual summary of the key information related to that application. These examples illustrate the wide-ranging and diverse potential applications of AI in the creative industries.

Sector overview and challenges to AI adoption

The UK Government defines the creative industries as “those industries which have their origin in individual creativity, skill and talent and which have a potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property.”⁹

They contribute significantly to the UK economy and are considered a strategic sector to secure the UK’s future industrial growth.¹⁰ In 2023, the sector’s estimated GVA was £125 billion, equal to 5.7% of the UK economy that year.¹¹ Over the last decade, the output of the creative sector has been growing over 1.5 times faster than the rest of the economy, and its workforce at almost 5 times the UK rate.¹²

Technologies like AI and the research and development underpinning them will be important drivers of future growth in this sector. In addition to the broader benefits AI offers businesses – such as supporting decision-making, improving customer experiences, and automating time-consuming tasks – the growing digitisation of content production, distribution, and consumption presents particularly interesting opportunities for companies in the creative industries. For example, AI technologies are already playing a role in shaping new forms of art and entertainment and are being used to accelerate and customise content creation processes.

To harness the potential for AI-driven growth in the creative industries, however, it will be important to advance our understanding of how these technologies can complement and support the creative work rather than replace it and advance in harmony with the needs of the sector. The nature of the creative sector raises challenges to the adoption of AI. Relative to other sectors, a significant barrier to AI adoption in the creative industries is the current uncertainty related to the interplay of AI and intellectual property (IP) protection. Effective IP protection is essential to the commercialisation of creative ideas. If businesses fear that their creations will be copied and their IP rights violated or do not know with certainty whether, by using a certain technology, they are violating existing IP rights, they will not be sufficiently incentivised to invest in innovation. Another widespread concern relates to the potentially negative impact of AI on creative work. Similarly to other sectors, professionals in the creative industries often stress the sector’s high exposure to AI-driven workforce displacement. As such, ensuring certainty around the legal copyright regime applicable to AI systems, especially to generative AI, and promoting ways for companies in the creative industries to explore how AI could be used to complement and improve – rather than replace – creative work will be very important levers to advance AI adoption in the sector.

9 UK Department of Culture, Media and Sport (2001). ‘Creative Industries Mapping Document.’ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/creative-industries-mapping-documents-2001>.

10 UK Department for Culture, Media and Sport (2023). ‘Creative industries sector vision: a joint plan to drive growth, build talent and develop skills.’ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/creative-industries-sector-vision/creative-industries-sector-vision-a-joint-plan-to-drive-growth-build-talent-and-develop-skills>.

11 GOV.UK (2024). *Using annual estimates from summed monthly GVA data* (DCMS). <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/dcms-economic-estimates-monthly-gva-to-mar-2024/using-annual-estimates-from-summed-monthly-gva-data-dcms>.

12 *Creative industries sector vision*. Cit.

Sector structure

'Creative industries' is an umbrella term used to indicate a range of different sub-sectors and it is not always easy to identify the core activities it comprises. Creative work often bridges formal categories of professional activity, thus making it difficult to divide the creative industries into distinct sub-sectors. While breaking down the creative industries into core areas is useful for analytical purposes, it is important to remember that the result can only be an approximation of a much more nuanced reality.

For the purposes of this briefing, we refer to the creative industries sub-sector classification proposed by the UK Government's Department for Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS). Based on the Creative Industries Economic Estimate Methodology,¹³ the creative industries can be broken down into 9 different sub-sectors:

- Advertising and marketing
- Architecture
- Crafts
- Design
- Film, TV, video, radio, and photography
- IT, software, and computer services
- Museums, galleries, and libraries
- Music, performing, and visual arts
- Publishing

While the scope of these sub-sectors is in many cases self-explanatory, it is worth noting that, based on the methodology developed by DCMS, 'Crafts' includes businesses that produce glass and ceramics, manufacture jewellery, work wood to create furniture and other objects, businesses forging metal, and 'other skilled workers'. 'Design' includes product, graphic, and fashion design. 'IT, software, and computer services' includes businesses developing software and computer games, providing IT and telecommunication services, and web design and development services.

¹³ Department for Culture, Media and Sport (2016). *Creative Industries Economic Estimates Methodology*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a8039af40f0b62302692413/CIEE_Methodology.pdf

AI applications for the creative industries

AI in the creative industries is reshaping the production, distribution, and consumption of creative content across a wide range of applications and sub-sectors. Some concrete examples include AI systems used to dub films in different languages, personalise the experience of users on websites and digital apps, produce targeted marketing assets, and even generate live commentary for events. These use cases show how companies in the creative industries are using AI not only to improve traditional business processes or provide better services to customers but also to explore new forms of creation. Below is a description of five AI use cases in the creative industries that we analysed using the framework presented in this **accompanying paper**.

Real-time sport commentary

Maximising fan engagement is a key concern for companies broadcasting live events. AI technologies can support companies in creating a more dynamic and informative user experience across their various platforms. For example, an AI system can be used to generate spoken commentary during sports events by creating bespoke narrations for video clips distributed across different platforms. As part of the commentary, the system could include technical analysis, insights, and predicted scores supporting a richer experience for the audience.

The AI system would have to be trained on audio, image, and video data collected from relevant sports events. The system could also be trained to learn the technical rules of a specific sport and generate in-depth, technical analysis for users who enjoy more comprehensive coverage.

Business challenge:

Improve audience engagement in sports broadcasting.

Solution:

An AI system delivers real-time technical commentary during a sport event, using the language and domain-specific vocabulary that a human commentator would use in that context.

Organisation

Type of use case

Service-centric

Business function

N/A

Data

Type of input data

Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Generation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Creative Industries

Sub-sector

Film, TV, video, radio and photography

Personalised size recommendations for fashion items

Purchasing clothing and other fashion items can be difficult for online customers. One of the main challenges for customers is to assess what item size and fit are right for them. AI technologies can be used by fashion retailers to enhance and personalise customer experience. This, in turn, can reward online retail companies with higher customer satisfaction and sales. For example, an AI system trained on data including product details such as style, size chart, and customer reviews, as well as anonymised data on

customer purchases could support customers in finding the most appropriate size of the items they consider for purchase. By combining this data with preferences provided by customers while shopping, the AI system can recommend the size of a fashion item that is more likely to be a good fit for a specific customer.

Business challenge:

Personalise customer experience in online fashion retail.

Solution:

An AI system helps customers shopping for clothes online find the best-fitting size for them in real time using the brand's sizing, product reviews and customer preferences.

Organisation

Type of use case

Product-centric

Business function

N/A

Data

Type of input data

Categorical, Numerical, Text, Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Recommendation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Creative Industries

Sub-sector

Fashion

Automated video broadcasting of hard-to-reach events

Broadcasting companies often must prioritise which events to focus on based on the limited resources available. The scarcity of employees with the required skills and knowledge can cause minor or hard-to-reach events to receive only partial coverage or go entirely unreported. AI technologies can support broadcasters in widening the range of live events that they can cover by automating some broadcasting tasks such as recording and editing video footage. For example, an AI system can process video

streams captured through static cameras strategically positioned to achieve contrasting shots, and frame, sequence, and select shots in real-time. By cropping images, switching camera views, and trying to follow the action of the event, the AI system reproduces the classical effect of a dynamic live event broadcasting. If proved to be scalable, similar systems could lead to acceptable multicamera coverage of previously untelevised types of events.

Business challenge:

Expand limited broadcast coverage capacity in film, TV, and video production.

Solution:

An AI system generates dynamic event broadcasting by framing, sequencing, and selecting video content in real-time, mimicking the work of a human operator.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Production

Data

Type of input data

Audio, Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Goal-directed action, Recognition and detection

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Proof of concept

Economic sector

Sector

Creative Industries

Sub-sector

Film, TV, video, radio and photography

Automated film dubbing

Adapting movies and TV series in multiple languages is a complex and resource-intensive task. AI can support film and video production companies by automating dubbing processes. For example, an AI system can be used to analyse the original audio of a video, create a script, and generate dubs emulating the emotional nuance of the original dialogue. Similar AI solutions offer several advantages for companies, including scalability, quicker turnarounds, and optimising production costs. By using only the original audio track

as input data, these AI systems can generate human-sounding voices in several languages, reproduce emotional intonations, and 'lip-synch' the new audio to the original video. When considering these systems, however, it is important to evaluate whether they perform to the expected levels of accuracy in the languages required. Their performance will likely be worse in languages that are less represented in their training datasets.

Business challenge:

Reduce the costs and time needed to create multi-language dubs in film, TV, and video production.

Solution:

An AI system generates multi-language dubs that emulate the emotional nuance of the original dialogue.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Production

Data

Type of input data

Audio

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Generation

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Creative Industries

Sub-sector

Film, TV, video, radio and photography

Automated social media asset generation

Content scaling and personalisation are important challenges in marketing and communication campaigns. AI technologies can be integrated into marketing processes to achieve broader reach and higher user engagement. For example, generative AI applications can support the creation of assets for digital communication campaigns, including content for social media platforms and longer-form text for websites and blogs. The ability of such applications to scale

content production enables companies to rapidly create a broad range of social media-ready assets to promote events, artists, and products across different platforms. AI models can be fine-tuned on the internal data of the company, including brand guidelines. They can then be integrated into systems that the company’s editorial team can prompt with text messages to create bespoke marketing and communication assets.

Business challenge:

Scale content creation and personalisation for marketing campaigns.

Solution:

An AI system can support editorial teams by creating assets for digital communication campaigns, including content for social media, websites and blogs.

Organisation

Type of use case
Process-centric

Business function
Marketing and advertising

Data

Type of input data
Text

Processing of personal data
No

AI system

AI system capabilities
Generation

Environment
Virtual

Readiness level
Operational

Economic sector

Sector
Creative Industries

Sub-sector
Advertising and marketing

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